

Role of the Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology (FNAC) in Salivary Gland Lesions and its Histopathological Correlation

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Abstract

Background: Salivary glands are exocrine glands that secrete saliva. Salivary gland system includes both major and minor glands. The study aimed to correlate the fine needle aspiration cytology diagnosis with histopathological features in population of Bihar, as catered by single tertiary care hospital NMCH Patna; Bihar.

Materials & Methods: This is prospective cross-sectional study conducted at department of pathology Nalanda Medical College and hospital, Patna. The study includes a total of (98) fine needle aspirates obtained from patients who visit our pathology department with various major salivary gland disorders. Both male and female patients with clinical and radiological findings were included in the study. Informed consent was obtained from the patient. FNAC was performed using 22-24 gauge needle and 5ml or 10 ml syringe by applying negative pressure. Smears were either wet fixed or air dried and stained by Hematoxylin and Eosin & Giemsa, respectively. All the results were recorded in Microsoft excel sheet and were subjected to statistical analysis using SPSS software.

Results: In current study salivary gland lesions were common between 31-40 years age group with mean age of 41.6yrs. There was male predominance with M: F of 1.57:1. In the present study benign lesions were 57.14% followed by non-neoplastic lesion 34.70% and malignant lesion 8.16% on FNAC examination of salivary gland lesions.

Conclusion: FNAC of salivary gland tumors has advantage to both patient and clinician because of its immediate results, accuracy, economy, and lack of complications. FNAC has high diagnostic accuracy of 97.14%, 95.71% and 97.14% for non-neoplastic lesions, benign tumors and malignant tumours (present study), which helps in appropriate therapeutic management.

Keywords: Cytology, Histopathology, Fine needle aspiration cytology

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Introduction

Salivary glands are exocrine glands that secrete saliva. The salivary gland system includes both major and minor glands. The parotid, submandibular, and sublingual are major salivary glands. Minor glands are present in the floor of the mouth, cheek and can be found in the lip, gingiva, hard and soft palate, tonsillar areas, and oropharynx. The salivary gland lesions can be: 1) non-neoplastic, like inflammation or cysts. 2) Neoplastic, either benign or malignant[1, 2]. Malignant can be primary or metastatic. The incidence of salivary gland tumours is 2-6.5% of all the head and neck tumors. Fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) is the most widely accepted

diagnostic tool for evaluating salivary gland lesions, due to their superficial location and easy accessibility of the target site. FNAC is a simple, rapid, economical, minimally invasive, and reliable diagnostic tool. FNAC has high sensitivity, specificity, and accuracy. FNAC is useful to categorise the lesions into inflammatory, reactive, benign, and malignant lesions, which are useful for appropriate therapeutic management [3,4]. It helps to avoid surgery in non-neoplastic inflammatory conditions. But many salivary gland tumours have overlapping cytomorphological features that present as challenging work to conclude with a precise diagnosis in some cases [5, 6].

Aim and Objectives:

- To evaluate the role of FNAC in the diagnosis of salivary gland lesions.
- To correlate FNAC diagnosis with histopathological features of salivary gland lesions.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: The present study was a prospective cross-sectional study.

Study Place: This study was conducted at the Department of Pathology in collaboration with Department of General Surgery, Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna.

Study Period: The study was carried out from October 2022 to July 2024.

Study Population: The present study included 103 patients of both genders but 5 patients were excluded due to hypocellular and bloody smear in FNAC. Finally ninety-eight (98) patients of both genders attending the OPD of Nalanda Medical College and Hospital with clinically and radiologically diagnosed various major salivary gland disorders were referred for FNAC in the Cytology section of the Department of Pathology, NMCH, Patna were included in the study. Out of 98 patients 70 patients had histopathological correlation and 28 patients were lost in follow up after FNAC. Informed consent was obtained from each patient.

Ethical Consideration: The study was approved by the research and ethical committee of the NMCH, Patna.

Inclusion Criteria

- Patients who have given written informed consent.
- All patients with salivary gland lesions diagnosed clinically and radiological findings and referred for FNAC.
- Available for follow-up.

Exclusion Criteria

- Smears with low cellularity, hypocellular smear.
- Smears obscured by blood, mucus, and inflammatory cells.
- Inadequate specimen.
- Uncooperative patients or patients who did not give consent and unable to attend follow-up

Procedure: Patient's age, clinical history, and USG findings were recorded. FNAC was performed using a 22–24-gauge needle and a 5 ml or 10 ml syringe by applying negative pressure. Smears were either wet-fixed or air-dried and stained by haematoxylin and eosin & Giemsa, respectively. The histopathological specimens were fixed overnight in 10 percent formalin and subjected to gross examination, processing, paraffin embedding, section cutting, staining by haematoxylin and eosin, and mounting by DPX.

Statistical Analysis: The data obtained was subjected to statistical analysis using a Microsoft Excel spread sheet and analysed using software Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) 25.0 version. The data were represented in tables and graphs. Categorical variables were summarised in frequency and percent distribution, and a chi-square test was performed by a statistician. A p-value less than 0.05 was deemed significant.

Results**Table 1: Age group wise distribution in salivary gland lesions**

Age group (In years)	Number of cases	Percentage
0-10 years	1	1.02
11-20 years	2	2.04
21-30 years	12	12.24
31-40 years	41	41.84
41-50 years	19	19.39
51-60 years	9	9.18
61-70 years	14	14.29
Total	98	100

Table 1 and graph 1, show that the maximum number of salivary gland lesions were seen in the age group 31-40 years (41.84%) with a mean age of

41.68 years with a standard deviation of 13.18 years. The age of patients ranged from 7 years to 68 years.

Graph 1: Age wise distribution of the patients

Table 2: Gender wise distribution of the salivary gland lesions

Gender	Number of cases	Percentage
Female	38	38.78
Male	60	61.22
Total	98	100

Table 2 shows that total of 98 patients were included in the study, in which there were 38 (38.78%) females and 60 (61.22%) males (M: F 1.57:1).

Table 3: Site wise distribution pattern

Site	Number of cases	Percentage
Parotid	64	65.31
Submandibular	34	34.69
Total	98	100

In Table 3 shows that in the present study, parotid gland was involved in 64 (65.31%) cases and submandibular gland was involved in 34 (34.69%) cases.

Table 4: Categorization of FNAC of salivary gland lesions

Category	FNAC	Percentage
Non-neoplastic lesion	34	34.70
Benign neoplastic lesion	56	57.14
Malignant neoplastic lesion	8	8.16
Total	98	100

Table 4 shows that in the present study, benign lesions were seen in 56 cases (57.14%), non-neoplastic lesion, 34 cases (34.70%), and malignant lesion, 8 cases (8.16%).

Table 5: Categorization of FNAC among site of salivary gland lesions

FNAC Lesions	Parotid	Submandibular	Total
Non-neoplastic lesion	15	19	34
Benign neo plastic lesion	46	10	56
Malignant neoplastic lesion	6	2	8
Total	64	34	98

Table 6: FNAC of Non-neoplastic salivary gland lesions

Non-neoplastic lesion	Parotid	Submandibular	Total
Chronic Sialadenitis	11	13	24
Sialadenosis	3	6	9
Lymphoepithelial cyst	1	0	1
Total	15	19	34

Table 6 shows that among the non-neoplastic lesions, chronic sialadenitis were seen in 24 (70.58%) cases, sialadenosis were seen in 9 (26.47%) cases and Lymphoepithelial cyst was seen in 1 case (2.94%).

Table 7: FNAC of Benign salivary gland lesions

Benign lesion	Parotid	Submandibular	Total
Pleomorphic adenoma	36	9	45
Warthin tumor	9	0	9
Oncocytoma	1	1	2
Total	46	10	56

Table 7, shows that among the benign lesions Pleomorphic adenoma are the most common constituting about 36 (64.28%) cases in parotid gland and 9 (16.07%) cases in submandibular gland. Warthintumor constitutes 9 (16.07%) cases in parotid gland and only 1 (1.78%) case of oncocytoma each in parotid gland and submandibular gland was found.

Table 8: FNAC of Malignant salivary gland lesions

Malignant lesions	Parotid	Submandibular	Total
Mucoepidermoid carcinoma	3	1	4
Adenoid cystic carcinoma	2	1	3
Acinic cell carcinoma	1	0	1
Total	6	2	8

Table 8 shows that among the malignant lesions Mucoepidermoid carcinoma, Adenoid cystic carcinoma and Acinic cell carcinoma seen in 4 (50.00%), 3 (37.50%) and 1 (12.50%) cases in parotid gland respectively.

Table 9: Categorization of Histodiagnosis of salivary gland lesions

Lesions	Histodiagnosis	Percentage
Non-neoplastic	19	27.14
Benign	42	60.00
Malignant	9	12.86
Total	70	100

Table 9 shows that in the present study, benign lesions were seen in 42 (60.00%) cases, followed by non-neoplastic lesion cases 19 (27.14%) and malignant lesion cases 9 (12.86%).

Table 10: Categorization of Histodiagnosis among site of salivary gland lesions

Histodiagnosis Lesions	Parotid	Submandibular	Total
Non-neoplastic	7	12	19
Benign	34	8	42
Malignant	7	2	9
Total	48	22	70

Graph 2: Histodiagnosis among site of salivary gland lesions

Table 10 and graph 2 shows the categorization of histodiagnosis among different salivary gland lesion sites. The data reveals that, out of 70 total cases, 48 lesions were identified in the parotid gland and 22 in the submandibular gland. Among these, 19 lesions were non-neoplastic, with 7 located in the parotid gland and 12 in the submandibular gland. Benign lesions were more prevalent, accounting for 42 cases, of which 34 were found in the parotid gland and 8 in the submandibular gland. Malignant lesions were less common, with 9 cases

in total, including 7 in the parotid gland and 2 in the submandibular gland.

Table 11: Histodiagnosis of Non-neoplastic salivary gland lesions

Non-neoplastic lesion	Parotid	Submandibular	Total
Chronic Sialadenitis	4	8	12
Sialadenosis	2	4	6
Lymphoepithelial cyst	1	0	1
Total	7	12	19

Table 11 shows that among the non-neoplastic lesions, chronic sialadenitis was seen in 12 (63.16%) cases, sialadenosis was seen in 6 (31.57%) cases and Lymphoepithelial cyst was seen in 3.16%.

Table 12: Histodiagnosis of Benign salivary gland lesions

Benign lesion	Parotid	Submandibular	Total
Pleomorphic adenoma	26	7	33
Warthin tumor	7	0	7
Oncocytoma	1	1	2
Total	34	8	42

Table 12 shows that among the benign neoplastic lesions, pleomorphic adenomas are the most common, constituting about 26 (78.57%) cases in the parotid gland and 7 (16.67%) cases in the submandibular gland. Warthin tumour constitutes 7 (16.67%) cases in the parotid gland. Oncocytomas are the least common, constituting about (2.38%) case in the parotid gland and 1 (2.38%) case in the submandibular gland.

Table 13: Histodiagnosis of Malignant of salivary gland lesions

Malignant lesion	Parotid	Submandibular	Total
Mucoepidermoid carcinoma	3	1	4
Adenoid cystic carcinoma	2	1	3
Salivary duct carcinoma	1	0	1
Acinic cell carcinoma	1	0	1
Total	7	2	9

Among the malignant lesions Mucoepidermoid carcinoma, Adenoid cystic carcinoma, Salivary duct carcinoma and Acinic cell carcinoma seen in 4(44.44%), 3(33.33%), 1(11.11%) and 1(11.11%) cases in parotid gland respectively.

Table 14: Correlation of FNAC and Histodiagnosis of Non-Neoplastic salivary gland lesions

FNAC for non-neoplastic lesion	Histodiagnosis for non-neoplastic lesion (The Truth)	
	Positive	Negative
Positive	TP=18	FP=1
Negative	FN=1	TN=50

Graph 3: ROC Curve for Non-neoplastic lesion

Sensitivity: 94.74%, specificity: 98.04%. Positive Predictive Value (PPV): 94.94%, Negative Predictive Value (NPV): 98.04%, Diagnostic Accuracy: 97.14%, Area Under Curve (AUC): 0.964, P value: <0.001.

Area Under the ROC Curve is significantly different from 0.5, and that therefore is evidence that the FNAC does have an ability to diagnose patients with (positive) and without disease (negative).

Table 15: Correlation of FNAC and Histodiagnosis of Benign salivary gland lesions

FNAC for Benign lesion	Histodiagnosis for Benign lesion (The Truth)	
	Positive	Negative
Positive	TP=41	FP=2
Negative	FN=1	TN=26

Sensitivity: 97.62%, Specificity: 92.86%, Positive Predictive Value: 98.35%, Negative Predictive Value: 96.23%, Diagnostic Accuracy: 95.71%, Area Under Curve (AUC): 0.958, P value: <0.001.

Area Under the ROC Curve is significantly differ from 0.5 and that therefore is evidence that the FNAC does have anability to diagnose patients with (positive) and without disease (negative).

Graph 4: ROC Curve for Benign lesion

Table 16: Correlation of FNAC and Histodiagnosis of Malignant salivary gland lesions

FNAC for Malignant lesion	Histodiagnosis for Malignant lesion (The Truth)	
	Positive	Negative
Positive	TP=8	FP=1
Negative	FN=1	TN=60

Sensitivity: 88.89%, Specificity: 98.36%, Positive Predictive Value: 88.89%, Negative Predictive Value: 98.36%, Diagnostic Accuracy: 97.14%, Area Under Curve (AUC): 0.936, P value: <0.001.

Area Under the ROC Curve is significantly differ from 0.5 and that therefore is evidence that the FNAC does have an ability to diagnose patients with (positive) and without disease (negative).

Graph 5: ROC Curve for Malignant lesion

Area Under the ROC Curve is significantly differ from 0.5 and that therefore is evidence that the FNAC does have an ability to

diagnose patients with (positive) and without disease (negative).

Figure 1 and 2 showing gross picture of pleomorphic Adenoma- well circumscribed, white glistening appearance on cut section

Figure 3 - Chronic sialadenitis-FNAC showing lymphocytes and histiocytes

Figure 4 - Pleomorphic Adenoma (4x) - FNAC showing single cells and poorly cohesive clusters in the background of chondromyxoidstroma.

Figure 5 - Mucoepidermoid carcinoma-FNAC showing scanty cellular material consisting of mucin secreting cells in dirty background

<p>Figure 6- Adenoid cystic carcinoma-FNAC showing hyaline globules Figure</p>	<p>Figure 7- Histology of normal salivary gland</p>	<p>Figure 8 - Histopathology section of Pleomorphic Adenoma showing cells arranged in irregular ducts in the background of chondromyxoidstroma.</p>

<p>Figure 9 - Histopathology section of Warthin tumor showing oncytic double layered epithelium surrounded by lymphoid cells.</p>	<p>Figure 10 - Histopathology of Mucoepidermoid carcinoma showing solid, sheets of epidermoid cells and mucus cells.</p>	<p>Figure 11 - Histopathology of adenoid cystic carcinoma showing tumor cells in duct and tubules and cystic spaces filled with mucin.</p>

Discussion

For the diagnosis of salivary gland neoplasms, fine needle aspiration is a safe and cost-effective method. FNAC can be done in an outpatient setting with a low risk of complications [7].

In the present prospective study, FNAC was performed on 103 cases during the study period from October 2022 to July 2024. Out of which, 5 patients were excluded from the study due to inadequate sampling and loss to follow-up. So, 98 patients were taken in the study group. 70 patients were followed up for histopathological confirmation.

In our study, salivary gland lesions were common in the 31-40 age group, with a mean age of 41.6 years. There was male predominance with M: F of 1.57:1.

Studies by various authors, however, found a male predominance and an age range of 8 to 68 years, with a mean age of 40 [8,9].

In the present study, benign lesions were 57.14%, followed by non-neoplastic lesions 34.70% and malignant cases at 8.16% on FNAC examination of salivary gland lesions. Among the non-neoplastic lesions, Chronic sialadenitis was 70.58% of cases, sialadenosis was 26.47% of cases and Lymphoepithelial cyst was seen in 2.94%. In the current study, 34.70% of the lesions seen on FNAC were non-neoplastic. This result is consistent with studies reporting between 20% and 72.9% [10, 11].

On histopathological examination we observed that benign lesions were seen in 60% of the cases, followed by non-neoplastic lesion cases (27.14%) and malignant lesion cases (12.86%).

Among the non-neoplastic lesions, chronic sialadenitis was seen in 63.16% of cases, sialadenosis was seen in 31.57% of cases and Lymphoepithelial cyst was seen in 3.16%. Among the benign neoplastic lesions, pleomorphic adenomas are the most common, constituting 78.57% of cases in the parotid gland and 16.67% of cases in the

submandibular gland. Arjun Singh et al. [4] found that malignant tumours constitute 21.66%, and pleomorphic adenoma was the common benign tumour, like the present study.

Warthin tumour constitutes 16.67% cases in the parotid gland. Oncocytoma constitutes about 2.38% case in the parotid gland and 2.38% case in the submandibular gland. In 9 cases of sialadenitis, 6 cases had histopathological correlation. A mixed population of lymphocytes, plasma cells, histiocytes, fibrous tissue fragments, ductal epithelial cells, and occasional acinar cells were the cytological features of chronic sialadenitis observed. 2 cases of Warthin tumour on histopathology were seen, which were diagnosed as chronic sialadenitis on FNAC. On reviewing the slide, there were abundant lymphoid cells in the background, which had led to the diagnosis of chronic sialadenitis on FNAC [12-14].

Jayaram et al. (1994) in their study of FNAC in 247 cases of salivary gland lesions, found the overall diagnostic accuracy of 91% for neoplastic lesions. The sensitivity rate in detecting malignant tumor was 87.8% and the specificity was 98%. There was 100% sensitivity rate for benign tumors [15].

Mourouzis C, et al. [16], determined the diagnostic value of fine-needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) for salivary gland tumors. Sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, positive prognostic value (PPV), and negative prognostic value (NPV) of FNAC for benign and malignant tumours separately were assessed and compared with histology. A total of 82 patients (46 male and 36 female) with salivary gland tumours, submitted to both FNAC and histology, were included. The mean age was 55 years. A total of 73 tumours were histologically diagnosed as benign and nine as malignant. FNAC identified 62 benign and seven malignant tumours but was inconclusive in 13 cases. The most common diagnosis of both histology and FNAC was pleomorphic adenoma. FNAC sensitivity, specificity, accuracy, PPV, and NPV were 98.3% and 100%, 87.5% and 100%, 97.1% and 100%, 98.3% and 100%, and 87.5% and 100% for benign and malignant tumours, respectively. FNAC is highly sensitive but moderately specific for the preoperative identification of benign salivary gland tumors. Its use as an initial diagnostic modality is warranted, thanks to its safety, rapidity, and lack of pain.

Limitations of study

A more accurate result could be obtained with a larger number of participants and a multicentric study.

Conclusion

FNAC of salivary gland tumors has advantage to both patient and clinician because of its immediate

results, accuracy, economy and lack of complications. FNAC has high diagnostic accuracy of 97.14%, 95.71% and 97.14% for non-neoplastic lesions, benign tumors and malignant tumours (present study), which helps in appropriate therapeutic management. The main advantage of this procedure is that it can be repeated at different sites in a particular lesion. FNAC is useful as an outpatient diagnostic procedure because of immediate diagnostic results. FNAC and histopathology complemented each other for diagnosis to be accurate for further management.

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